

SOIL PROPERTIES OF TYPICAL IRRIGATED SEROZEM SOILS BY ELEVATION LEVEL BASED ON GIS TECHNOLOGY

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Abstract. The article presents data on the content of humus, phosphorus, potassium, physical clay, dry matter and bulk density of typical irrigated serozem soils distributed in the Jizzakh region at various altitudes using GIS technology.

Key words: Soil, humus, phosphorus, potassium, physical clay, dry matter, bulk density, GIS technologies, altitude, typical soil.

Introduction. Nowadays, with its numerous capabilities, GAT is being used in agriculture, as in other sectors. In particular, it is used to perform tasks such as agricultural environmental management, planning, and decision-making. Based on GAT, a number of works are being carried out on remote sensing, monitoring water quality, microbiological activity, and plant distribution in the agricultural sector [1].

Using traditional methods to conduct various studies on soil takes some time. As computer technology has developed, new methods have emerged to map the properties of soil. Remote sensing, global positioning using GAT programs, and analysis of various properties over time are methods [2].

Research object and methods. Typical irrigated serozem soils of the "Laylak Uya" massif of the Zamin district of the Jizzakh region were selected as the research object. The study was carried out on the basis of the Instructions for conducting soil surveys and compiling soil maps for maintaining the state land cadastre [3] and generally accepted methods. General chemical and physicochemical soil analyses were performed according to generally accepted methods based on the manuals of Ye.V. Arinushkina [4]. Analysis based on

geographic information systems was performed using the ArcGIS program and its Geostatistical Analyst modules.

Research results and their analysis. The humus content of the study area was determined by altitude. In particular, the highest humus content (0,81-1,2%) was observed in irrigated areas at low altitudes (480-530 m) and amounted to 489,74 hectares, while a decrease in humus content was observed in areas at medium (531-580 m) and the highest altitudes (581-634 m). According to the results, soils with low and medium humus content in terms of hectares prevail at low, medium and high altitudes.

Exchangeable potassium plays an important role in plant life, contributing to good plant growth and development and increasing disease resistance. The highest exchangeable potassium content (201-300 mg/kg) was found in the area of 359,9 hectares of soils at altitudes of 480-530 m. A decrease in exchangeable potassium content was observed at medium (531-580 m) and high (581-634 m) altitudes. Its highest content is found in areas with low altitudes and moderately supplied groups.

Mobile phosphorus, that is, phosphorus, is essential for good plant development and increases the strength of stems and roots. It was found that at low (480-530 m) altitudes, the area occupied by mobile phosphorus (16-30 mg/kg) was 307,5 hectares, while at medium and high altitudes, the amount of mobile phosphorus decreased.

Picture 1. Map of the elevation of the “Laylak uya” massif above sea level

In terms of mechanical composition, medium loamy (31-45%) soils occupy the largest part of the irrigated land at low altitudes (480-530 m), accounting for 443,8 hectares. It was found that medium loamy areas are less common at higher altitudes. In terms of mechanical composition, medium loamy soils are widespread in large areas at low and medium altitudes, and their share is dominant over soils of other mechanical compositions. 49,6% of the irrigated land area of Jizzakh region is considered medium loam [5].

In irrigated soils, salinity is mainly determined by the amount of dry matter in the soil (this only includes determination by dry matter). At low altitudes (480-530 m), the area with a dry matter content of 0,136-0,160% was found to be 204,2 hectares. At medium and high altitudes, the area with a dry matter content of 0,136-0,160% was found to be less than a hectare.

At low altitudes, the area in hectares with a dry matter content of 0,136-0,160% in soil composition was higher, while at medium and high altitudes, the area with a dry matter content of 0,136-0,160% decreased.

Picture-2

Picture-2. Dynamics of changes in soil properties at different altitudes of irrigated soils in the selected reference area.

The bulk density of the soil indicates its density and water permeability. It was found that 507,55 hectares of irrigated land at low altitudes (480-530 m) had a bulk density of 130-139 g/cm³, which is within the acceptable range for soil density at this altitude.

Conclusion. In conclusion, it is worth noting that, according to the results of the study, it was found that in the study area, areas belonging to the group with an average (0,81-1,2%) soil humus content were higher at low altitudes (480-530 m).

This indicator was not high at medium and high altitudes. Areas with a mobile phosphorus content of (16-30 mg/kg) occupy a large part of the territory. The amount of exchangeable potassium was (201-300 mg/kg). Areas with a physical clay content of (31-45%), a bulk density of 130-139 g/cm³, and a dry residue content of 0,136-0,160% were identified, occupying large areas at low altitudes

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